

IoT-Based On-the-Fly Visual Defect Detection in Railway Tracks

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ABSTRACT

In India, railway transportation service is the cheap and the majority convenient mode of passenger transport and also for long-distance and suburban traffic. The main cause of the accidents happened in railways are railway track crossing and unrevealed crack in railway tracks. Therefore, there is a need to have new technology which will be robust, efficient, and stable for both crack detection in railway track as well as to object detection. This project discusses a Railway track crack detection using sensors and is a dynamic approach that combines the use of a GPS tracking system to send alert messages and the geographical coordinate of location. Arduino Microcontrollers used to control and coordinate the activities of this device. The Indian Railways consists one of the largest railway networks in the whole world, criss-crossing over 1, 15,000 km in distance, all over India. However, with regard to reliability, dependability, and passenger safety of Indian Railways is not up to the global standards. Among other factors, the cracks are developed on the railway tracks due to absence of the inefficient timely detection. Our work involves a project that aims of designing a railway crack detection system (RCDS) using an Ultrasonic Sensor, The GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications), GPS (Global Positioning System) and Arduino based module whose implementation is an efficient method of detecting the cracks which are present in the tracks and thus avoiding derailment of the trains. In this project, we are using an ultrasonic sensor which is used to find the crack in the railway track And also capable of alerting the authorities in the form of SMS messages along with location by using GPS and GSM modules.

Keywords: Crack Detection, Railway, Transport

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In India railways transportation service is the cheap and the majority convenient mode of passenger transport and also for long distance and suburban traffic. The main cause of the accidents happened in railways are railway track crossing and unrevealed crack in railway tracks. Therefore, there is a need to have new technology which will be robust, efficient and stable for both crack detection in railway track as well as object detection. This project discusses a Railway track crack detection using sensors and is a dynamic approach which combines the use of GPS tracking system to send alert messages and the geographical coordinate of location. Arduino Microcontrollers used to control and coordinate the activities of this device.

Railway is one of the most significant transportation modes of our country but it is a matter of great sorrow that, railway tracks of our country are very prone. That's why, a vast number of accidents are occurred every year due to this primitive type of railway tracks and as the consequences of those accidents we lose huge number of lives every year.

These types of incidents motivate us to think over the above mentioned issue and take necessary steps to protect those lives. Through our proposed system, we need to establish more modern and secure railway system. Besides this, there is no such type of technology or system in our country which can stop the collision between two trains coming from the opposite direction of each other on the same track. We actually think over this matter and motivated to do so. Moreover natural disaster can throw any object on the rail track which cannot be removed very quickly in the remote area. We thought if our system can detect those object or barrier and inform to the control room then they can take necessary steps to avoid accident. Figure1 depicts the crack on track. The Rail transport is growing at a rapid pace in India. It is one of the major mode of transport but still our facilities are not that accurate, safer as compared to international standards. A survey on the internet states that about 60% of all the railway accidents is due to derailments, recent measurements shows that about 90% are due to cracks on the rails. Hence, it is not safer for Human Life. This needs to be at the utmost attention. These goes unnoticed and the properly maintenance of tracks is not done.

In country like India, where majority of people depend on railways for transportation, if a crack in railway track is not detected during the early stages they may lead to derailment causing heavy loss to human life and property. In this paper a crack detection system is proposed which detects the crack without human intervention and sends the location of fault to the authorized personnel using GSM. Crack detection by this method can be done during both day and night time and exact location of fault can be obtained

In the current rail system, it is more necessary to have safety elements in order to avoid accidents. One of the important causes that can provoke serious accidents is the existence of obstacles on the tracks either fixed or mobile and the cracks that are happened to the track. This project deals with one of the efficient methods to avoid train collision and obstacles detection and crack detection. This project aims for the detection of cracks in railway tracks, distance between the tracks and the presence of humans on railway tracks. The design of system consist a Global Position System (GPS) module, Global System for Mobile (GSM) modem, In proposed system, the ultra-sonic sensor sensors are used for detect the crack in the rail track. If any cracks or obstacles are detected on the railway tracks or if any change in the distance between the two tracks, the longitude and latitude of the track location is messaged to the nearest railway station using GPS and GSM modems. The proposed system is compared with the traditional measuring systems, where it stands as an efficient and cost effective system for railway applications.

1.2 OBJECTIVE

- Advanced project
- SMS Alert
- GSM and GPS based project
- Rail track crack detection

LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 LITERATURE SURVEY

Indian Railway has developed a vandal-proof warning system for unmanned level crossings which is working satisfactorily for the last three months on Coimbatore-Mettupalayam section [1]. In Indian railways, there are a total of 28,607 level crossings across the country of which 19,267 are manned and 9340 are unmanned. According to the action plan, the railways is focusing on eliminating almost all the unmanned level crossing in the next 3-4 years .

With this focus it is desirable to study various techniques to control the operation of gates at level crossings. Many journal papers are available which proposes automated railway gate system [3-7]. These papers discuss different options such as automatically controlled railway gate at the level crossing, railway track switching mechanism and the movement of the train using sensors, micro controllers for reduction of railway accidents and controller for stepper motor which operates the opening and closing of railway gates at the railway crossings. K Vidyasagar et al

designed a system which uses ultrasonic sensors to identify objects on the track and accordingly control signal is generated and transferred to the control room via communication protocol to control the movement of train in railway track. Pwint et al [9] describes the automatic railway gate control system using PIC microcontroller for saving precious human lives and preventing major disasters in railway track. An Arduino based control system for the opening and closing of railway gates with IR sensors for detection of train is proposed by Krishnamurthi et al .

A detailed introduction about the technology adopted in railways is described with the disadvantages of manually operated railway warning systems at level crossings by Dewangan et al . Mahmud et al discuss the design and implementation of an automated railway gate control system which detects the train by analyzing the reflected waves, produces alarm, controls light signal and gate

METHODOLOGY

Ultrasonic sensor is used to detect the crack in the rail track with measuring the distance from track to sensor. Ultrasonic technique is the most effective method which detects cracks on a railway track. An android application will be developed to intimate about the rail cracks . GPS module when the crack is detected, relevant geographical location coordinates will sent to the nearest station. This recording and sending of coordinates are done by GPS module. GPS network used by cell phones provides a low cost, long range wireless communication channel for applications that require connectivity rather than higher data rates. GSM is use for the send in sms from the fault the railway track crack detection

SYSTEM DESIGN

BLOCK DIAGRAM

3.3 WORKING

The project block diagram which contains following process

1. Initially the tracks are being continuously monitored with the help of sensor, which is used to detect the crack in the track.
2. This monitoring is done with the help of ultrasonic sensor
in order to sense the minor changes also which can be quite difficult with other sensors.
3. Whenever the crack gets detected with the help of ultrasonic sensor it passes the alert of crack found to the Arduino microcontroller.
4. The Arduino microcontroller will perform the process assigned to it accordingly.
5. The process mainly includes positioning, sending and alerting through the help of GPS module.
6. As the message gets delivered to the Railway Authority, the alert is to be taken into account and
important measures must be taken by them in order to avoid future incidents and miss happenings which can lead to loss of human life and also to major injuries.

H/W AND S/W DESCRIPTION

4.1 HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

ARDUINO

Arduino Architecture:

Arduino's processor basically uses the Harvard architecture where the program code and program data have separate memory. It consists of two memories- Program memory and the data memory. The code is stored in the flash program memory, whereas the data is stored in the data memory. The Atmega328 has 32 KB of flash memory for storing code (of which 0.5 KB is used for the bootloader), 2 KB of SRAM and 1 KB of EEPROM and operates with a clock speed of 16MHz.

Arduino Architecture

LCD DISPLAY

LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) screen is an electronic display module and find a wide range of applications. A 16x2 LCD display is very basic module and is very commonly used in various devices and circuits. These modules are preferred over seven segments and other multi segment LEDs. The reasons being: LCDs are economical; easily programmable; have no limitation of displaying special & even custom characters (unlike in seven segments), animations and so on.

A **16x2 LCD** means it can display 16 characters per line and there are 2 such lines. In this LCD each character is displayed in 5x7 pixel matrix. This LCD has two registers, namely, Command and Data.

The command register stores the command instructions given to the LCD. A command is an instruction given to LCD to do a predefined task like initializing it, clearing its screen, setting the cursor position, controlling display etc. The data register stores the data to be displayed on the LCD. The data is the ASCII value of the character to be displayed on the LCD. Click to learn more about internal structure of a LCD.

VOLTAGE TRANSFORMER

One of the main reasons that we use alternating AC voltages and currents in our homes and workplace’s is that AC supplies can be easily generated at a convenient voltage, transformed (hence the name transformer) into much higher voltages and then distributed

The reason for transforming the voltage to a much higher level is that higher distribution voltages implies lower currents for the same power and therefore lower I^2R losses along the networked grid of cables. These higher AC transmission voltages and currents can then be reduced to a much lower, safer and usable voltage level where it can be used to supply electrical equipment in our homes and workplaces, and all this is possible thanks to the basic **Voltage Transformer**.

VOLTAGE REGULATOR IC 7805:

7805 is a **voltage regulator** integrated circuit. It is a member of 78xx series of fixed linear voltage regulator ICs. The voltage source in a circuit may have fluctuations and would not give the fixed voltage output.

LM7805 PINOUT DIAGRAM

The **voltage regulator IC** maintains the output voltage at a constant value. The xx in 78xx indicates the fixed output voltage it is designed to provide. 7805 provides +5V regulated power supply. Capacitors of suitable values can be connected at input and output pins depending upon the respective voltage levels.

VOLTAGE REGULATOR IC 7812:

7812 is a **voltage regulator** integrated circuit. It is a member of 78xx series of fixed linear voltage regulator ICs. The voltage source in a circuit may have fluctuations and would not give the fixed voltage output.

The **voltage regulator IC** maintains the output voltage at a constant value. The xx in 78xx indicates the fixed output voltage it is designed to provide. 7812 provides +12V regulated power supply. Capacitors of suitable values can be connected at input and output pins depending upon the respective voltage levels.

DC MOTOR

A DC motor in simple words is a device that converts direct current (electrical energy) into mechanical energy. It's of vital importance for the industry today, and is equally important for engineers to look into the **working principle of DC motor** in details that has been discussed in this article. In order to understand the **operating principle of dc motor** we need to first look into its constructional feature.

The very basic construction of a dc motor contains a current carrying armature which is connected to the supply end through commutator segments and brushes and placed within the north south poles of a permanent or an electro-magnet as shown in the diagram below. Now to go into the details of the **operating principle of DC motor** it's important that we have a clear understanding of Fleming's left hand rule to determine the direction of force acting on the arm

BUZZER

A buzzer takes some sort of input and emits a sound in response to it. They may use various means to produce the sound; everything from metal clappers to electromechanical devices.

A buzzer needs to have some way of taking in energy and converting it to acoustic energy. Many buzzers are part of a larger circuit and take their power directly from the device's power source. In other cases, however, the buzzer may be battery powered so that it will go off in the event of a mains outage. Some devices that provide emergency power have buzzers on them so that the user knows that they are running on backup power and not on mains power.

ULTRASONIC SENSOR

Ultrasonic sensors emit short, high frequency sound pulses at regular intervals. These propagate in the air at the velocity of sound. If they strike an object, then they are reflected back as echo signals to the sensor[5], which itself computes the distance to the target based on the time-span between emitting the signal and receiving the echo. If the signal from the ultrasonic sensor the motors will change the direction of the grass cutter. 5. Working: The design contains the micro controller, solar panel DC motors, battery makes a robotic. The whole components are

interfaced to micro controller. First the ultrasonic sensor will send the signal if the signal gets back then it sends the information to the micro controller and this will control the movement of the DC motors. If there is no object in front of the robotic vehicle both the motors will have movement and it is indicated to us using the led light[6]. Any object or human detected in front of it the direction changes to the right or left based on the direction the other

Base station subsystem

GSM [cell site](#) antennas in the [Deutsches Museum](#), Munich, Germany

GSM is a [cellular network](#), which means that [cell phones](#) connect to it by searching for cells in the immediate vicinity. There are five different cell sizes in a GSM network—[macro](#), [micro](#), [pico](#), [femto](#), and [umbrella cells](#). The coverage area of each cell varies according to the implementation environment. Macro cells can be regarded as cells where the [base station antenna](#) is installed on a mast or a building above average rooftop level. Micro cells

are cells whose antenna height is under average rooftop level; they are typically used in urban areas. Picocells are small cells whose coverage diameter is a few dozen metres; they are mainly used indoors. Femtocells are cells designed for use in residential or small business environments and connect to the service provider's network via a broadband internet connection. Umbrella cells are used to cover shadowed regions of smaller cells and fill in gaps in coverage between those cells.

Cell horizontal radius varies depending on antenna height, antenna gain, and propagation conditions from a couple of hundred meters to several tens of kilometres. The longest distance the GSM specification supports in practical use is 35 kilometres (22 mi). There are also several implementations of the concept of an extended cell where the cell radius could be double or even more, depending on the antenna system, the type of terrain, and the [timing advance](#).

Indoor coverage is also supported by GSM and may be achieved by using an indoor picocell base station, or an [indoor repeater](#) with distributed indoor antennas fed through power splitters, to deliver the radio signals from an antenna outdoors to the separate indoor distributed antenna system. These are typically deployed when significant call capacity is needed indoors, like in shopping centers or airports. However, this is not a prerequisite, since indoor coverage is also provided by in-building penetration of the radio signals from any nearby cell.

GSM carrier frequencies CAPACITORS

A capacitor or condenser is a passive electronic component consisting of a pair of conductors separated by a dielectric. When a voltage potential difference exists between the conductors, an electric field is present in the dielectric. This field stores energy and produces a mechanical force between the plates. The effect is greatest between wide, flat, parallel, narrowly separated conductors.

An ideal capacitor is characterized by a single constant value, capacitance, which is measured in farads. This is the ratio of the electric charge on each conductor to the potential difference between them. In practice, the dielectric between the plates passes a small amount of leakage current. The conductors and leads introduce an equivalent series resistance and the dielectric has an electric field strength limit resulting in a breakdown voltage.

The properties of capacitors in a circuit may determine the resonant frequency and quality factor of a resonant circuit, power dissipation and operating frequency in a digital logic circuit, energy capacity in a high-power system, and many other important aspects.

5.1 ADVANTAGES

- Quick tracking of the cracks on the railway tracks and can rectify easily.
- Easy to automate unmanned level crosses.
- Can avoid accidents due to trains coming on the same tracks.
- Reduces chances of human error.
- Safety and quality of services.

5.2 APPLICATION

- To automate unmanned level crosses.
- To track cracks on railway tracks.
- Its cost very low compared to existing system
- Very accurate detection
- Accidents reduced

CONCLUSION:

As per the study the existing systems are time consuming as well as uneconomical. The proposed system is not only overcome these problems but also improve accuracy and crack detection in rails. It is the most economical solution provided in order to achieve good results of railways of our country in order to minimize the stats of accidents caused. There by possible to save precious lives of passengers and loss of economy. It also saves the time and money for identification of crack.

FUTURE SCOPE:

This will help to detect cracks immediately and reduce the possibilities of any mishappening. Since the system would be automatic and will require less manual intervention, the utmost efficiency of the system can be ensured. However, this system finds difficulty in sensing an internal crack in the railway track. The idea can be implemented in large scale, in the long run, to facilitate better safety standards for rail tracks and provide effective testing infrastructure for achieving better results in the future.

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